

Astragalus glycyphyllos: extraction condition optimisation, extract standardisation and solid dosage form preparation

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Abstract

Astragalus glycyphyllos is used in folk medicine as a diuretic, antispasmodic, antihypertensive and anti-inflammatory agent. A number of flavonoids and saponins have been identified in the species, which exhibit antioxidant, cytoprotective, neuroprotective, hepatoprotective and immunostimulating activity. This makes the species promising for use in medical practice. In the present study, the conditions for obtaining a dry extract from the aboveground part have been optimised in order to include it in appropriate dosage forms. Two extraction methods were used – Soxhlet apparatus and percolation. The influence of solvent type and temperature on the amount of active and ballast substances during extraction was studied. The liquid extracts were dried by lyophilisation and standardised by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS) with high resolution for triterpene saponins. A comprehensive technology for obtaining a dry extract from the aerial part of *A. glycyphyllos*, easily applicable under production conditions, as well as a method for quantitative determination of triterpene saponins, was proposed. The obtained standardised extract was successfully used for the preparation of hard gelatine capsules, which were technologically characterised. The results demonstrate the overall feasibility of obtaining a dosage form.

Keywords

analysis, cycloartane saponins, extraction optimisation, solid dosage form, standardisation

Introduction

Since time immemorial, humankind has used plants as a reliable and accessible source of substances – nutritional or with medicinal properties – to maintain health or fight diseases. Despite the wide range of compounds accumulated in plants, a small part of them is directly absorbable. These are mainly primary metabolites, such as carbohydrates, lipids and proteins. They have mainly nutritional value (Kandar 2021). Secondary metabolites in a plant, such as

phenolic compounds, terpenes or alkaloids, are often present in low quantities, which makes direct consumption of the plant unsuitable. In addition, the structure of the plant cell and the large amount of cellulose in plants are obstacles to the extraction of biologically active substances (BAS) during the digestive process (Lakshmanan 2022).

This requires that plant substances be extracted and BAS obtained in a form suitable for humans. In traditional medicine, medicinal plants are mainly extracted with water, most often resulting in infusions or decoctions. These

aqueous extracts are unstable, both chemically and microbiologically. Water is a polar extraction agent, but in its presence hydrolysis is possible, as well as microbial growth (López-Bascón and Luque de Castro 2020). These prerequisites have led to the use of alcohol–water mixtures for extracting plant material in production conditions (Jha and Sit 2022). The resulting liquid extracts, despite the good solubility of BAS in them and their rapid resorption, are not preferred, as they take up space and weigh too much (Zhang et al. 2020). In most cases, dry extracts are obtained from them, which are used in solid dosage forms, such as tablets or hard gelatine capsules (Mudrić et al. 2021).

Astragalus glycyphyllos (Fabaceae) is the only species of the genus that is widely used in folk medicine in many European countries, including Bulgaria (Linnek et al. 2011; Lysiuk and Darmohray 2016). It has been proven that the plant accumulates, like other representatives of the genus *Astragalus*, three groups of BAS – polysaccharides, flavonoids and triterpene saponins. In the folk medicine of Bulgaria, infusions and decoctions from the aboveground part of the species are used as a diuretic, antispasmodic and antihypertensive agent, and for liver diseases (Krašteva et al. 2023). In a series of studies, it has been established that extracts of *A. glycyphyllos* exhibit hepatoprotective (Shkondrov et al. 2015), neuroprotective (Stambolov et al. 2023) and antiviral effects (Hinkov et al. 2023). It has been proven that the content of triterpene saponins, mainly of the cycloartane type, is largely responsible for these activities (Shkondrov et al. 2023). In a previous study, tablets (Shkondrov et al. 2023) were formulated from a dry extract obtained in laboratory conditions. In addition to the valuable and promising effects of the plant extracts, its wide distribution throughout the country, as well as the size of the populations (Asyov et al. 2012), make it a reliable resource with potential practical application.

Despite the large number of studies on the species, there is no systematic analysis of the possibilities for obtaining an extract on a larger scale that contains a high amount of saponins so that it can be used for industrial purposes.

The aim of this study was to: 1) optimise the conditions for obtaining a dry extract from the plant; 2) standardise the obtained extract against a suitable plant marker by UHPLC – HRESIMS; 3) select a suitable solid dosage form.

Materials and methods

Plant material

The aerial parts of *A. glycyphyllos* L. were collected during the flowering period in July 2021 from a locality in Vitosha Mt., on the outskirts of Sofia, Bulgaria. A specimen of the plant was deposited in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Biology, Sofia University, under No. SO107613. The plant material was cleaned of mechanical impurities, dried at room temperature, then ground using a grinder and sieved through a mesh size of 3 mm.

Extraction and preparation of dry extracts

Two methods were used to extract the plant material: percolation – in a one-litre percolator, and extraction in a Soxhlet apparatus with a vessel volume of 2 L, connected to a 5 L round-bottom flask. The plant material (200 g) was placed in factory sleeves made of pressed filter paper. Extraction took place in cycles, the length of each depending on the type of solvent used, or rather, its boiling temperature. The flask was heated in an automatic heating mantle. The liquid extract obtained by one of the two methods was distilled on a rotary vacuum evaporator to obtain a thick extract, which was transferred to a vessel suitable for lyophilisation. A freeze-dryer Alpha 3-4 LSC basic (Martin Christ, Germany) was used, and the lyophilisation cycle is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters of the lyophilisation.

Phase	Duration, h	Pressure, mbar	Temperature, °C
Main	90	0.200	-110
Final	6	0.015	-110

Quantitative determination of saponins in extracts

An accurately weighed amount of the dry extract (0.2000 g) was placed in a 10.0 mL volumetric flask. It was dissolved in an ultrasonic bath (frequency 35 kHz) for 10 min with MeOH. After tempering, the flask was made up to the mark with the same solvent. About 2 mL of the extract were transferred to a microcentrifuge tube, centrifuged for 10 min at 15,000 × g, and the supernatant was separated and filtered through a membrane filter (0.22 µm, PVDF) into an autosampler vial. All samples were stored at -22 °C until analysis.

A UHPLC system (Dionex UltiMate 3000 RSLC, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) connected to a QExactive™ Plus Orbitrap mass spectrometer with a heated electrospray ionisation (HESI) ion source (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) was used. The parameters of the full-scan MS were: resolution 70,000 (at 200 m/z), AGC target 3e6, maximum IT 100 ms, and scan range 250–1700 m/z. The ion source operated at -2.5 kV and 320 °C (capillary and probe), with 38 arbitrary units (a.u., as per the Exactive Tune software, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) of sheath gas and 12 a.u. of auxiliary gas (both N₂); S-Lens RF level 50.0. A Kromasil C18 column (1.9 µm, 2.1 × 50 mm, Akzo Nobel, Bohus, Sweden) was used, maintained at 40 °C, and eluted with H₂O + 0.1% HCOOH (A) and MeCN + 0.1% HCOOH (B) (0.3 mL/min). The gradient elution is presented in Table 2.

Three saponins (Table 3) isolated from the aboveground part of the same species were used as references: 17(R),20(R)-3β,6α,16β-trihydroxycycloorthanyl-23-carboxylic acid 16-lactone 3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside (AGOS1) (Shkondrov et al. 2020), 3-O-[α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)]-β-D-xylopyranosyl]-24-O-α-L-arabinopyran-

Table 2. Gradient elution programme.

Time, min	H ₂ O + 0.1% HCOOH (A), %	MeCN + 0.1% HCOOH (B), %
0	90	10
1.4	90	10
7	70	100
8.5	70	100
13	90	10

Table 3. Reference compounds.

Abbreviation	Purity, %	<i>m/z</i> (-), type
AGOS1	99.80	623, [M+HCOO] ⁻
AGOS3	97.83	947, [M+HCOO] ⁻
AGOS9	98.05	813, [M-H] ⁻

nosyl-3β,6α,16β,24(*R*),25-pentahydroxy-20(*R*)-cycloartane (AGOS3), and astrachryoside A (AGOS9) (Stambolov et al. 2023). The MS-SIM scan mode was used with a set range of *m/z* corresponding to [M-H]⁻ as well as their adduct ions.

The following criteria for identification were adopted. A peak with a retention time equal to that of the reference in both positive and negative modes in the chromatogram of the extract should be observed. The compound corresponding to the peak should give the same base ion as the standard. The base-peak ion observed in the extract should fragment in the same way as the reference.

Thermo Scientific Xcalibur®, version 4.2.28.14, was used to collect data when constructing the calibration curve and to calculate the results.

Capsule preparation and characterisation

Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC; Vivapur 102) was purchased from JRS Pharma (Rosenberg, Germany). Empty dried gelatine capsules (size 0) were kindly provided by Sopharma AD (Sofia, Bulgaria). A fixed amount of dry extract of the aerial parts of *A. glycyphyllos* and varying quantities of MCC were dry-mixed in a mixer to create a homogeneous, randomised powder mixture (Table 4).

Table 4. Composition of powder mixture (capsule filling material).

Sample code	Dry extract (mg/capsule)	MCC (mg/capsule)
S1	150	–
S2	150	50
S3	150	100
S4	150	150

The flowability of the powder mixtures was assessed by a commonly used pharmacopoeial test method, Eur. Ph. 2.9.36 (Council of Europe: European Directorate of Quality of Medicines 2023), namely the angle of repose. The method characterises the resistance to movement between particles. In brief, the powder is allowed to flow freely through a fixed funnel onto a stationary horizontal surface. The angle of repose formed between the height

(*h*) of the powder cone and its base (*D*) is calculated by the equation:

$$\text{Tan}(\Theta) = \frac{h}{0.5 \times D}$$

The results are interpreted in relation to the general scale of flowability for the angle of repose (Θ°) as follows: 55–60° very poor; 46–55° poor; 41–45° passable; 36–40° fair (aid not needed); 31–35° good; and 25–30° excellent.

The powder mixture with optimal flow properties was filled into dry gelatine capsules (size 0) using a hand-operated capsule filling machine. The prepared capsules were characterised for uniformity of mass and disintegration as described in Ph. Eur. 11.0 (methods 2.9.5 and 2.9.1, respectively).

Results and discussion

Choice of extraction method

When extracting the plant material with 80% MeOH using two extraction methods (percolation and Soxhlet apparatus), the amount of extractable matter (Ph. Eur. 11, general methods in pharmacognosy) was almost the same (Table 5).

Table 5. Extractives in both methods.

Method	Duration, h	Extractable matter, %
Percolation	168	43
Soxhlet extraction	20	44

In further studies, the second method was applied, since the extraction time was 8 times shorter than percolation.

Preparation of dry extracts

Extracts were obtained with methanol at different concentrations in a Soxhlet apparatus. The extraction time at different methanol concentrations varied due to differences in the boiling point of the MeOH–H₂O mixtures (Table 6).

Table 6. Extraction time in a Soxhlet apparatus.

Extract	Solvent mixture	T _{boiling} , °C	Duration, h
A	10% MeOH	86	26
B	20% MeOH	80	24
C	50% MeOH	75	22
D	80% MeOH	70	20

After distillation of the solvent, the concentrated extracts were lyophilised (see Materials and methods). Extraction with 80% MeOH (D) yielded the highest amount of extract – 46.04% (Table 7).

Table 7. Amount of extract obtained by extraction with MeOH at different concentrations.

Extract	Solvent mixture	Extractable matter, % (per dry material)
A	10% MeOH	29.00
B	20% MeOH	27.00
C	50% MeOH	20.39
D	80% MeOH	46.04

Quantification of saponins by UH-PLC-HRESIMS

The identification of the three cycloartane-type saponins to be quantified in the extracts was performed in SIM mode, with a set value of the corresponding m/z (see Table 3). The apparatus used for the analysis, as well as the reference substances, is described in Material and methods. The validation of the quantitative method with respect to the three saponins (AGOS1, AGOS3 and AGOS9) was performed according to approved ICH standards (Guideline 2005).

Calibration curve

The standard solutions of the saponins were prepared in MeOH, as presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Concentration of standard solutions used to construct calibration curves.

Level	AGOS1, ng/ml	AGOS3, ng/ml	AGOS9, ng/ml
5	1000	1020	980
4	600	612	588
3	100	102	98
2	50	51	49
1	10	10.2	9.8

Each of the solutions was injected three times, and the arithmetic mean of the three measurements was used to select the corresponding level in order to construct each calibration line. The chromatograms of the standard solutions are presented in Figs 1–3.

From these chromatograms, the retention times of the saponins were determined as a mean value (Table 9).

Table 9. Retention times of standard substances (n = 3).

Saponin	t_R mean, min
AGOS1	5.59 ± 0.02
AGOS3	5.84 ± 0.01
AGOS9	6.70 ± 0.02

Figure 3. Chromatogram of AGOS9 standard solution (980 ng/ml).

One microlitre of each solution was injected into the system three times to obtain the calibration curve points of the respective compound. After integrating the area under the peaks obtained for each standard solution, calculating the arithmetic mean, and correlating the concentration, the graphs presented in Figs 4–6 were obtained.

After applying linear regression, the equations of the lines and the regression coefficients were obtained (Table 10).

Figure 5. Calibration curve of AGOS3.

Figure 6. Calibration curve of AGOS9.

Table 10. Equations of the lines and regression coefficients for the saponins.

Compound	Equation	r^2
AGOS1	$y = 14734 + 15559.9x$	0.9997
AGOS3	$y = 284229 + 28495.6x$	0.9990
AGOS9	$y = -110953 + 51025.4x$	0.9964

where y is the signal and x the concentration in ng/ml.

Specificity

The specificity of the method towards saponins was investigated using a blank sample. After analysis of the chromatogram obtained by injection of blank samples (MeOH), no peaks were recorded that corresponded to the three saponins at their retention times.

Limits of detection and quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) was determined based on a mathematical calculation using the equation: $y_{LOD} = y_b + 3S_b$, where: y_{LOD} is the LOD, y_b is the detector signal when injecting a blank sample, and S_b is the standard deviation of the mean statistical value of the detector signal when injecting a blank sample. The limit of detection for the developed method is 0.0001 ng/ml for the three compounds. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was calculated using the equation: $y_{LOQ} = y_b + 10S_b$, where: y_{LOQ} is the LOQ, y_b is the detector signal when injecting a blank sample, and S_b is the standard deviation of the mean statistical value of the detector signal when injecting a blank sample. The limit of quantification for the method is 0.001 ng/mL for all.

The developed analytical method was applied for the quantitative determination of the three triterpene-type sa-

ponins in the lyophilised extracts. The procedure for preparing the samples for analysis is described in the Materials and methods section. When injecting the samples into the UHPLC–MS system, the chromatograms presented in Figs 7–10 were obtained.

After identifying the peaks corresponding to the three saponins in the samples, their amounts were determined using the linear regression equations described in Method validation. Using MS mode to quantify saponins has some advantages over the classical UV methods. The lack of a strong chromophore in their molecules requires working at low wavelengths (202–210 nm), but the solvents used for HPLC have their own absorbance (Wang et al. 2022). The targeted m/z values used to quantify the compounds are much more specific. In addition, analysing complex plant matrices without purification requires accurate analyte identification (Ahuja et al. 2023). The results are presented in Figs 11–13.

The amount of AGOS1 in extract C was the highest – 1.09%, while in extract A it was the lowest (0.12%). The most suitable solvent for the compound was 50% MeOH (Fig. 11).

The amount of AGOS3 in extract C was the highest – 1.34% (Fig. 12). The saponin was not detected in the extract obtained with 10% MeOH (A); therefore, the most suitable solvent was again 50% MeOH.

The amount of AGOS9 in extract C was the highest – 0.66% (Fig. 13). The substance was not detected in the extract obtained with 10% MeOH (A). The 50% MeOH was the most suitable solvent for extracting this saponin.

In conclusion, it can be summarised that, regardless of polarity differences, the three substances were most fully extracted from the plant material with 50% MeOH. The differentiated content of saponins in the four studied extracts is presented in Fig. 14.

In addition to determining the amount of plant markers individually, the total content of triterpene saponins in the obtained extracts was also measured using the same method (Fig. 15).

The summarised data from the quantitative determination of saponins in the four extracts are presented in Table 11.

It was found that in extract C, obtained with 50% MeOH, the content of total cycloartane saponins was the highest (3%). This finding is due to the appropriate polarity of 50% MeOH for dissolving the saponins.

Figure 7. Chromatogram of extract A.

Figure 8. Chromatogram of extract B.

Figure 9. Chromatogram of extract C.

Figure 10. Chromatogram of extract D.

Figure 11. AGOS1 content in the samples.

Figure 13. AGOS9 content in the samples.

Figure 12. AGOS3 content in the samples.

Figure 14. Differential content of the three saponins in the samples.

Figure 15. Content of total saponins in the extracts.

Table 11. Saponin content in the extract obtained.

Extract	AGOS1, %	AGOS3, %	AGOS9, %	Total saponins, %
A	0.12 ± 0.03	0	0	0.12 ± 0.03
B	0.59 ± 0.01	0.61 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.02	1.51 ± 0.02
C	1.09 ± 0.02	1.34 ± 0.03	0.66 ± 0.01	3.09 ± 0.02
D	0.45 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.01	0.51 ± 0.02	2.02 ± 0.01

Like many polar compounds, their solubility is better in higher ratios of water (Akbari et al. 2023). A practical plant marker for standardising an extract from the plant is the saponin AGOS1. The substance has a proven structure and was found in all extracts.

Preparation of hard gelatine capsules for peroral delivery of dry *A. glycyphyllos* extract

The first step in capsule preparation was to select the powder mixture with optimal flowability, as good flow is a prerequisite for the uniform distribution of the single dose of plant extract in the individual capsule units. The results for the angle of repose are given in Table 12.

Table 12. Powder mixture flow.

Sample code	Angle of repose (°)	Flow
S1	49.5 ± 1.8	Poor
S2	44.9 ± 2.1°	Passable
S3	40.1 ± 1.3	Fair
S4	35.2 ± 1.1	Good

The angle of repose was determined using the fixed-funnel method in accordance with Ph. Eur. 11.0, 2.9.36 (Council of Europe: European Directorate of Quality of Medicines 2023). The optimised sample blend S4 (composed of 1:1 dry extract and microcrystalline cellulose) exhibited an angle of repose of 35.2° ± 1.1°, indicating good flowability. It was selected for capsule preparation.

Fifty capsules of size 0 were filled with S4 using a hand-operated capsule filling machine. The average fill

weight was targeted to achieve a final capsule content of 300 mg of total powder blend, corresponding to approximately 150 mg of dry extract per capsule unit. The obtained capsules were characterised according to the requirements of the European Pharmacopoeia 11.0 (Council of Europe: European Directorate of Quality of Medicines 2023) for average mass (2.9.5) and disintegration (2.9.1). The results of the tests performed are presented in Table 13.

As evident, the mean capsule mass was 306 mg (± 4.6 mg), with all individual masses within ±7.5% of the average, thus conforming to pharmacopoeial specifications. The prepared capsules also met the requirements for disintegration.

The formulation of hard gelatine capsules is a preferred delivery platform for peroral administration of dry plant extracts, as they offer several advantages over other solid dosage forms, including improved patient compliance, better taste-masking, and enhanced stability of hygroscopic or sensitive plant materials. In addition, their capacity for precise dosing and protection of hygroscopic extracts from environmental degradation makes capsules highly preferable for delivering standardised botanicals (Hutchison and Viswanath 2008). The use of hard gelatine capsules as a dosage form is associated with yet another advantage – they allow the use of standardised extracts that are rapidly available for absorption, owing to their fast dissolution (Gullapalli and Mazzitelli 2017).

Taken together, these findings support the appropriateness of this formulation approach for the manufacture of *A. glycyphyllos* dry extract capsules in compliance with Ph. Eur. requirements, ensuring reliable peroral delivery of these valuable saponins.

Conclusion

A complete technological scheme for obtaining a dry extract from the aerial parts of *A. glycyphyllos* was developed. The most appropriate method for extraction of this plant material was by a Soxhlet-type extractor with 50% MeOH as the solvent. The most appropriate chemical marker for standardising the dry extract was the cycloartane triterpenoid saponin AGOS1, since it was present in the highest amount and found in every extract. According to international standards, a method for its quantitation was created and validated. The applicability of the prepared standardised dry extract was demonstrated through the technological formulation of hard gelatine capsules.

Table 13. Technological parameters of capsules.

Composition	Average mass (mg)		Disintegration (min)	
	Experimentally established	Acceptable under the Pharmacopoeia	Experimentally established	Acceptable under the Pharmacopoeia
Extract (150 mg)	306 ± 4.6	300 ± 7.5%	3 min	Up to 30 min
MCC (150 mg)		(277.5 ÷ 322.5 mg)		

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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